

EVALUATION OF TMC INTERFACE PROPERTIES BY THE SLICE COMPRESSION TEST

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial shear properties in SiC fiber-reinforced titanium matrix composites were evaluated with the slice compression test which imposes fiber/matrix interfacial shear stresses by compressing a unidirectional composite between a hard, high modulus anvil and a soft, low modulus one. Composites tested contained low volume fractions of accurately-aligned and uniformly-separated fibers. Two fiber interfaces were investigated, one with a low shear strength, the other with a higher shear strength. Results indicate that the stress distributions are too complex to be amenable to analysis and that the test has a low sensitivity to changes in interface properties.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of advanced composite materials is strongly influenced by the mechanical behavior of the fiber/matrix interface. Optimization of interface properties in titanium matrix composites has lagged behind other aspects of composite development. Methods for evaluating interfacial shear properties, which are essential for their optimization, are currently inadequate due to the difficulty of imposing shear stresses without other, more complicated stress distributions.

A diagram of the slice compression test appears in Figures 1 and 2, showing a uniaxial fiber reinforced composite compressed between a rigid, high modulus anvil, and a deformable, low modulus anvil. Since the deformable anvil flows plastically under the applied load, it tends to impose an approximately constant traction on the fibers and the matrix, whereas the hard anvil applies a greater traction to the fiber because of the fiber's higher modulus. The approximately uniform stress boundary condition imposed by the soft anvil develops shear stresses at the fiber-matrix interface near that anvil and causes debonding. The fibers protrude from the composite, intruding into the deformable material and leaving a record of their maximum protrusion.

Figures 1 and 2. Slice compression experimental setups with (1) swivel plate alignment system and (2) rigidly-aligned compression anvils.

In an effort to develop a technique to measure interfacial shear strengths in titanium matrix composites, slice compression testing was performed on two types of composite with widely different interface properties, as determined by single fiber fragmentation tests. These composites included Textron, SCS-6 silicon carbide fibers in a Ti-6Al-4V matrix and Amercom, AC3, triplex "soft" carbon coated fiber in the same matrix.

As fibers intrude into the deformable anvil, work hardening occurs and different tractions are exerted on the fiber and matrix. Quantitation of these tractions poses a difficult problem for either analytical or numeric methods, and suggests an experimental approach. When the load is released, fibers may retract some distance into the composite, limited by friction forces along the interface.

Data acquisition techniques included acoustic emission detection of interfacial debonding, contact and non-contact profilometric measurement of maximum and residual fiber protrusion, and measurement of the extent of interfacial debonding. Specimens with different thicknesses were tested to investigate the influence of fiber aspect ratio on data acquisition and analysis. Interfacial shear properties were compared with results obtained by single fiber fragmentation testing.

EXPERIMENTAL

Previous attempts to apply the slice compression test to ceramic matrix composites by other researchers^{1,2} were unsuccessful due to a number of experimental difficulties. Among these were the variation in fiber orientation in the composites tested, variation in fiber diameter along the length of each fiber, and variation in fiber spacing resulting in a non-uniform local fiber volume fraction. The brittle ceramic matrices used were susceptible to crushing during the test, invalidating the results. Substantial void volume fractions in the composites complicated the stress distributions. Specimens were found to rotate during testing, giving in a much greater indentation depth on one side of the specimen than on the other, resulting in a serious non-uniformity in the imposed stresses.

Model composites were used in the present study to eliminate many of these problems. These models had uniform, low volume fractions of fibers which were accurately oriented orthogonally to the plane of the composite surface. Void-free titanium matrix composites were investigated, with no danger of crushing the matrix material.

Initial experiments with a large radius swivel plate as shown in Figure 1 produced specimen rotations and non-uniform indentation depths. Small misalignments were amplified into large differences in indentation depth from one side of the sample to the other. To correct this problem, the swivel plate was replaced by a fixed anvil support as shown in Figure 2, with all surfaces accurately flat and parallel. The resulting indentations were uniform to within 1-2°. The specimens were compressed between anvils consisting of silicon nitride ("hard") and 260 brass ("soft").

Composite specimens were fabricated by vacuum hot pressing for 3 hours at 925 °C and 2500 psi pressure. Specimen preforms consisted of 4 - 120mm X 35 mm X 1.27mm thick sheets of Ti-6Al-4V with fiber retention and protection grooves machined in with a specially-constructed shaping apparatus at 1.27mm spacings³. Fibers 40 mm in length were laid into the grooves at the center of the preform plates and secured with a fugitive polymer binder. The top surfaces of the fibers were beneath the plane of the preform plates so that no asperity contact pressures that might cause damage were imposed on them before the plates began to flow at elevated temperature.

Specimens were sectioned with a low-speed diamond saw and polished with diamond paste using firm laps, including glass plates, to produce surfaces with very low relief between the fibers and matrix. With proper care the fibers surfaces can be kept to within 60-120 nm of the specimen plane, thereby reducing complications from initial work hardening of the soft anvil near the fibers.

SLICE COMPRESSION DATA ACQUISITION

Data that may be acquired during the slice compression test include acoustic emissions, if any, during the debonding process, the maximum fiber protrusion, as measured by the depths of the indentation in the deformable anvil, the residual fiber protrusion, the specimen geometry, particularly thickness and fiber distribution, and the maximum load applied.

An attempt was made to detect debonding by acoustic emission. The apparatus was acoustically isolated by supporting both anvils from lead cylinders. Acoustic data were monitored with a Locan AT acoustic emission system. Although acoustic emissions were detected, in some cases more emissions were detected with neat matrix specimens than with specimens containing debonding fibers. Therefore, although emissions in the appropriate amplitude range and number occurred in some cases, it cannot be unambiguously stated that these emissions arose from fiber debonding.

Fiber protrusion was measured with a Dektak II, contact surface profilometer and a Zeiss LSM 310 confocal microscope. Measurements were performed on composite specimens before and after testing, on the faces of the composite adjoining the hard and deformable anvils, and on the indentations left in the deformable anvil. A confocal microscope profile map of a protruded fiber is shown in Fig. 3

Figure 3. Surface profile map of protruded fiber end produced by confocal optical microscopy.

The results obtained by contact profilometry were compared with those obtained by confocal microscope profilometry to check the validity and resolution of both kinds of measurements. Measurements obtained from 15 fibers in the center row, of three by both techniques are shown plotted in Fig. 4. In all but one case, the results are in agreement to within approximately 0.1 micron. The one discrepancy may be ascribed to human error by the contact profilometer operator (Kralik). Alternatively, the fiber may have retracted due to mechanical contact between measurements.

The data in Fig. 4 were obtained from an A3CB fiber specimen that was slightly tapered from end to end, resulting in a non-uniform indentation into the brass anvil. This non-uniformity resulted in the large difference ($>5.0\mu$ to $<1.0\mu$) in protrusion length shown here.

The protrusion lengths of the fibers were compared with the intrusion depths of the brass anvil to determine whether fiber retraction was a significant factor. Fibers that are protruded from the matrix at high imposed stress might be expected to be under tension when that stress is removed,

causing them to retract back into the matrix. The fibers in the composites before testing were under residual compression strains of approximately 0.4%, however. Protrusion of the fibers might be expected to cause a release of these strains and a net stress too low to cause any significant retraction. Fig. 5. compares the fiber protrusion length after release of the load and the depths on the indentations left in the brass anvils. It can be seen that the differences between these lengths are small (0.1μ) and nearly random, with slightly greater average indentation depths than protrusion lengths.

Figure 4. Fiber protrusion lengths for A3CB fiber in tapered specimen, measured by contact (Dektak) and non-contact (confocal microscopy) profilometry.

Figure 5. Fiber protrusion and brass anvil indentation depths for the same set of A3CB fibers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fiber protrusion lengths and brass intrusion depths for an SCS-6 in Ti-6Al-4V composite are shown in Fig. 6. A close correspondence can be seen between the fiber protrusion length and intrusion depths in all cases except fiber number 6, row 3 of the composite, which appears to have retracted. A substantial variation can be seen between fibers near the center of the specimen, and those near the two ends. Greater tractions exerted at the ends due to the distribution of stresses in the deforming brass appear to have resulted in the greater protrusions at the specimen ends.

An additional complication arises from lateral forces due to Poisson's expansions and friction. As the soft anvil material deforms plastically during loading, the composite remains within its elastic limit. This brings about a difference in Poisson's ratios of approximately 0.5 for the anvil and 0.33 for the composite. This mismatch produces very large lateral forces at points away from the center of symmetry of the specimen.

Figure 6. Fiber protrusion and brass indentation depths for SCS-6 fiber in Ti-6Al-4V matrix. The composite consisted of three rows of twelve fibers each spaced 1.27 mm on center.

Figure 7. Indentation in brass produced by fiber away from the specimen axis of symmetry.

Fig. 7 shows the result of these lateral forces on the soft anvil, a fiber gouging into it and digging to the side. A surface profile map of the same region (Fig. 8) showed that the fiber originally indented at the left of the image and then the anvil material flowed sideways to the left under it. The stresses imposed at the fiber/matrix interface by this process clearly include substantial and nonuniform normal stresses along with the shear component. The fiber that produced this indentation is shown could be seen to have been debonded in an asymmetric fashion as a result of the complex loading.

Figure 8. Surface profile map of indentation shown in Fig. 7, produced by a fiber near the specimen end, away from the axis of symmetry.

Numerous complications exist in the mechanics of both the composite, the anvil and the overall system. The distribution of tractions imposed by the soft anvil on the composite face should ideally be uniform, distributed evenly due to plastic flow of the anvil. In fact, however, the traction on the protruding fiber end is different from that on the matrix regions due to anvil work hardening and constraint changes during protrusion. Various approaches have been taken to model this traction distribution. Hsue^{4,5} has assumed that the tractions are approximately uniform across the composite face. Lu and Mai⁶ have assumed a distribution corresponding to incipient flow of the soft anvil material, and come up with a higher traction along the fiber end, than on adjacent matrix areas.

Since it is difficult to address these complications by either analytical or numeric methods an effort to obtain experimental insight into the traction distribution was made. Single silicon carbide fibers were indented into brass anvil plates and the load displacement curves recorded. The specimens were prepared for this purpose by polishing the end of a single fiber composite produced by hot pressing and etching away 1-2 fiber diameters of matrix material with Kroll's reagent. The specimens were gripped in a universal testing machine and the protruding fiber indented into the brass. Since the anvil material adjacent to the indenting fiber was not constrained against flow by matrix material, as would be the case with an indented composite, the stress conditions are not identical. The load/displacement curves were found to be approximately linear over the very short distance involved in slice compression indentation, on the order of 2 microns for a 150 micron

diameter fiber. At indentation depths approaching one fiber diameter, nonlinear behavior resembling a power law relation was observed, and stresses greater than 1.5 GPa were observed.

Attempts were made to measure the extent of interfacial debonding by optical microscopy of fibers that were exposed by digestion with Kroll's reagent before and after testing. Although a greater tendency toward debonding was observed at the end of the fibers indented into the soft anvil, some debonding was also observed at the other end, and at random points along the fiber length. It is thought that nonuniform release of residual stresses during the digestion process may initiate debonding and introduce these artifacts.

The fiber protrusion length was found to be a function of specimen thickness, as shown in Figure 9. The data shown are for both SCS-6 in Ti-6Al-4V, and for A3CB in Ti-6Al-4V matrix. As can be seen, from the data for SCS-6, thinner specimens resulted in shorter protrusion lengths, apparently approaching a limit as thickness increases.

Figure 9. Fiber protrusion length for SCS-6 and A3C fibers in Ti-6Al-4V matrix vs specimen thickness.

The most serious problem for the application of slice compression to TMC's appears to be its insensitivity to interfacial properties. The protrusion lengths shown in Fig. 6 for A3CB fibers are only a few tenths of a micron greater than those expected for SCS-6 fibers in the same matrix and at the same specimen thickness. This small difference must be measured in fibers that are 150 μ in diameter. In contrast, single fiber fragmentation measurements of these same interface properties show many more fragmentation events, on the order of 3-4 times as many, for the SCS-6 fibers than for A3CB, indicating a large difference in interfacial shear transmissibility.

CONCLUSIONS

Although many of the experimental difficulties associated with slice compression testing in ceramic matrix composites do not preclude its application to metal matrix composites, additional complications remain. These complications particularly include the lateral flow of the anvil with respect to the composite resulting from Poisson's ratio mismatches which impose large normal stress at the fiber/matrix interface. The small differences in protrusion between very low and high friction coefficient interfaces also indicates that the technique is unlikely to provide information with as great a sensitivity as that provided by other interface characterization techniques.

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